

Recommended citation: Haldi, T. C., & Richey, M. (2018). Developing "Architecture and Systems Engineering" Program: an MIT, Boeing, and NASA Collaboration. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 824-831). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672708.

Developing “Architecture and Systems Engineering” Program: An MIT, Boeing, and NASA Collaboration

TC Haldi (12 pt, Arial font bold)

Senior Director, MIT xPRO (12 pt, Arial font)

MIT Open Learning (12 pt, Arial font)

Cambridge, MA, USA (12 pt, Arial font)

E-mail: thaldi@mit.edu (12 pt, Arial font)

M. Richey (12 pt, Arial font bold)¹

Associate Technical Fellow and Chief Learning Scientist (12 pt, Arial font)

Leadership, Learning and Organizational Capability, The Boeing Company (12 pt, Arial font)

Seattle, WA, USA (12 pt, Arial font)

E-mail: michael.c.richey@boeing.com(12 pt, Arial font)

Conference Key Areas: University-Business cooperation, Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning, Open and Online Engineering Education

Keywords: systems engineering, professional development, online education

INTRODUCTION

As global STEM related organizations try to redefine and reform the highly demanding space of workplace education within the digital era, learning and development (L&D) professionals face challenges such as building employee expertise, enhancing skill development, driving meaningful business results, and aligning training programs with organizations’ strategic imperatives. “Nearly all experts agree that machine learning, AI, and workplace automation following developments in these fields will replace many jobs worldwide. But estimates of the risk posed by automation have varied considerably.”[1] According to the latest working paper on “Automation, skills and

¹ Corresponding Author (All in Arial, 10 pt, single space)

Initials Last name

e-mail address

training”[2] released by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) almost 50% of the jobs discussed in the paper are expected to be “significantly affected by automation”, while among them 14% are facing high risk, 32% medium risk, and 26% low risk [1,2]. Vis-à-vis all upcoming changes, employees also seek to augment their professional skills, advance their formal education, and grow their careers. All of these challenges need to be addressed in a timely, scalable, and cost-effective manner; and many universities have already started exploring the university-business cooperation model as one more possible path towards catering to future L&D needs [3].

Within this framework MIT xPRO, a group within Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), was launched to address these corporate learning needs by collaborating with industry partners in order to develop and deliver online and blended programs targeted to professional learners seeking to expand their knowledge and build their skills.

1 THE PROGRAM

In 2015 MIT xPRO partnered with Boeing and NASA to develop “Architecture and Systems Engineering: Models and Methods to Manage Complex Systems” [4]—a four-course online program leading to a professional certificate from MIT.

The program blends academic theory with industry case studies to help systems engineers design, manage, and optimize complex systems. Throughout the program, students are presented with the latest practices in systems engineering—including how models can enhance system engineering functions and how systems engineering tasks can be augmented with quantitative analysis—and they explore those practices in the context of organizations applying them today. By the end of the program, students are expected to be able to frame systems architecture as a series of decisions, which can be actively sorted, managed, and improved to suit their organization’s needs.

The program is targeted to engineering professionals, directors, and senior managers across a number of industries—aerospace, automotive, medical devices, consumer products, nuclear power, etc.—who are working on the design, architecture, and engineering of complex, cyber physical systems and want to innovate in and optimize their systems.

Currently two instances of the program are offered—a private instance for Boeing and NASA employees, and a public instance available for open enrollment. Students in either instance have the flexibility of taking individual courses (each 4 weeks in duration), or pursuing the professional certificate (4 courses, 17 weeks in duration).

2 COURSES

2.1 Course one: Architecture of Complex Systems

As systems continue to grow in scale and complexity, understanding and managing system complexity is a critical challenge engineers have to face regularly. Course One is designed to help engineers address changes which induce, propagate, and amplify risk in the increasingly complex products and services they are required to develop. In this course, students get a solid grounding in complex systems, analysis of complex systems, and complexity management. [4]

By the end of the course, students should be able to: [4]

- Define a system and articulate examples of things that are and are not systems. Apply system thinking to provide perspective on a given project.
- Define and illustrate the system boundary and use it to identify system interfaces.
- Provide constructive criticism on the system architecture representations of others, including checking for completeness and consistency.
- Articulate more solution-neutral and less solution-neutral framings of a problem, and evaluate how solution-neutral to be for a given problem.
- Construct a Design Structure Matrix (DSM), either by analyzing the design or by converting a graph of the system. Construct a process DSM and identify how it is different from a design DSM.
- Describe rework and articulate the principles by which an analysis of change propagation could be conducted from a database of changes.
- Define the deliverables of the architect, with references to architectural frameworks and their career examples.

Industry examples are drawn from: Boeing, NASA, General Motors, Man Truck and Bus AG, Apple, General Electric, and U.S. Air Force.

2.2 Course two: Models in Engineering

Engineering practice is full of models—from equations to prototypes to simulations. In this course, students are expected to gain a comprehensive understanding of practical and conceptual modeling considerations so they can make more effective decisions supported by modeling analysis. [4]

By the end of the course, students should be able to: [4]

- Explain what types of models exist in engineering and how they can be organized into an overall taxonomy.
- Enumerate the purposes for which models are created in engineering and evaluate the success of modeling for those purposes against their own career experience.

- Evaluate the credibility and fidelity of existing models using a set of clear criteria.
- Evaluate and explain whether it is better to pursue a single model or an ensemble of models in support of a specific problem/decision. This includes the resolution of conflicts when multiple models provide contradictory results.
- Understand the basic principles of verifying and validating models.
- Examine the tradeoffs between the use of physical and virtual prototypes for system verification, validation, and testing. Decide when to invest in additional modeling versus additional physical testing of systems.
- The content deeply engages learners and maximizes learner outcome via videos, readings, discussions, individual and team projects, ungraded and graded problems, peer review, and self-assessment.

Industry examples are drawn from: Boeing, NASA, DSO National Laboratories Singapore, DfR Solutions, General Motors, and General Electric.

2.3 Course three: Model-Based Systems Engineering

This course introduces students to the intent, representations, and functions of Model-Based Systems Engineering (MBSE). Students are expected to create MBSE representations of a system and to articulate the purpose of the representations. From this foundation of MBSE, the course transitions to a discussion of the management challenges of MBSE – model repositories, model curation, and model integration. Students analyze best practices of MBSE in industry through case studies, which enable them to develop judgment about what functions are possible to accomplish with MBSE. [4]

By the end of the course, students should be able to: [4]

- Distinguish the differences between MBSE and traditional systems engineering.
- Describe the intent and basic structure of SysML and interpret a simple SysML model.
- Critique a project's implementation of MBSE using a set of criteria.
- Build a model management plan.
- Reference existing industry examples of MBSE to anchor choices about the scope of MBSE to undertake, and communicate potential approaches using industry examples as signposts.

Industry examples are drawn from: Boeing, NASA, Jet Propulsion Lab, PTC, IBM, U.S. Air Force, MITRE Corporation, MAN Truck and Bus AG, Uber, and General Motors.

2.4 Course four: Quantitative Methods in Systems Engineering

Organizations around the world strive to use quantitative information methods in their systems engineering practices, but many struggle to implement them effectively. This course covers the fundamentals of quantitative methods in systems engineering and provides basic how-to instruction for implementing these methods. [4]

By the end of the course, students should be able to: [4]

- Evaluate concept alternatives in order to recommend a preferred alternative.
- Structure a trade study.
- Identify the multiple key cost and benefit criteria that frame a system decision opportunity.
- Construct a value hierarchy for a stakeholder/beneficiary/decision-maker to inform system design decisions.
- Articulate the core concepts of value-based thinking.
- Choose the relevant axes and representations for a tradespace.
- Interpret the results of a tradespace.
- Identify the fuzzy Pareto front in a tradespace.
- Perform a sensitivity analysis.
- Critique a decision analysis model by identifying sources of uncertainty and variation.

Industry examples are drawn from: Boeing, NASA, Penn State, and General Motors.

3 LEARNING DESIGN

MIT's motto "Mens et Manus", in English translates as "mind and hand", and has always been the driving teaching approach within the MIT campus and beyond [5]. The goal of this online program (and all MIT xPRO offerings for the corporate market) is to bridge the "knowing-doing gap," connect theory to practice, and make the materials skill oriented and application focused.

The following pedagogical strategies are blended to best achieve the learning objectives of the program and individual courses.

- Instructivism (captured by the LEARN column in *Fig. 1*): Teacher-centered learning where the instructor defines the learning goals and presents relevant content, including mandatory readings. Examples in the program include:
 - Tutorial videos enhanced with animations and graphics
 - Text-based pages with supplementary pictures, charts, exhibits and illustrations
 - Assigned chapter readings from assigned textbook
- Constructivism (captured by the APPLY and PRACTICE columns in *Fig. 1*): Learning-by-doing approach that encourages learners to "construct" their own

understandings through the act of creating. Ideally learners create an artifact that a real-world practitioner would create. Examples in the program include:

- Project-based work
- Graded and ungraded practice activities
- Anchored Instruction (captured by the LEARN and APPLY columns in *Fig. 1*): A learning experience is “anchored” in a central narrative such as a case study or piece of media. Learners see new knowledge or skills applied in context. At regular intervals, learners utilize the knowledge or skills outlined in the anchor in various parallel contexts enabling them to cognitively situate instructivist content within the central narrative. Examples in the program include:
 - Case studies
 - Project-based work
- Connectivism (captured by the CONNECT column in *Fig. 1*): Learning through others. Social interaction emphasizes the cycle of sharing and consuming information as a member of a social learning network as a means of refining mental models and forming interdisciplinary connections. Learners are encouraged to make connections and identify patterns between knowledge nodes through their interactions with their peers. They are also encouraged to seek answers to questions from the community, with course staff supporting these interactions. Examples in the program include:
 - Discussion forum collaborations
 - Project-based work collaboration
 - Polls and word clouds with real-time results

Fig. 1. Program developer estimates, regarding how students are expected spend their time across the different content areas of course one, Architecture of Complex Systems.

4 PROGRAM DEVELOPMENT

MIT, Boeing, and NASA collaborated for one year to develop this program. The first step was for MIT to develop a high level outline of the proposed curriculum accompanied by design suggestions in regards to how the content would be delivered in an online medium. The outline then was reviewed by Boeing and NASA stakeholders for feedback and design input. After several iterations, the three partners came to an agreement regarding the curriculum and the project moved into production mode. Regular check-in meetings were held throughout the year and prototyping, alpha, and beta testing phases were conducted.

5 CURRENT STATE AND FUTURE WORK

The “Architecture and Systems Engineering” program has already been offered 4 times, and to date the program has been completed by over 4,500 students (2,500 Boeing/NASA students, 2,000 open enrollment student. The fifth program run will take place in September 2018. As the program gains traction and recognition, we see an increase in the number of companies enrolling large groups of employees (50-100), while some are requesting private site licenses of the content to deploy across their organizations.

The “Architecture and Systems Engineering” program was a very positive and rewarding experience for MIT, Boeing, and NASA. Key ingredients for success include: having a shared vision of the partnership opportunity, the ability to identify talent and leaders on all sides who were capable of crossing boundaries between academia and industry, strong communication, clear intellectual property goals, and a commitment to investing in each other over the long-term. Furthermore, the “Architecture and Systems Engineering” program has so far been a positive indicator that application-focused, skill-based instruction for workplace learning could take place effectively online. It also supports the initial idea that the academic/industry educational model can be achieved in a scalable and cost-effective manner, although of course a lot of space for improvement still exists. Moreover, MIT has found that this particular model is repeatable.

According to our experience to date the opportunity space for academic/industry partnerships is enormous and offers a new, compelling model for workplace learning. As the space is still new and unexplored, a lot of work remains to be done in order to finalize and suggest a state of the art course and program model. However, our positive findings so far have kept all partners motivated and encouraged to keep exploring this path. Along these lines MIT and Boeing have already partnered on two more programs—one on Additive Manufacturing and another on Engineering Leadership. MIT has also partnered with IBM to develop a 4-course program on Quantum Computing.

REFERENCES

- [1] Pagano, D. (2018) *OECD estimates 14% of jobs at high risk of automation*. As retrieved from <https://jwel.mit.edu/news/oecd-estimates-14-jobs-high-risk-automation> on May 3rd, 2018.

- [2] Nedelkoska, L. and Quintini, G. (2018), “Automation, skills use and training”, OECD Social, Employment and Migration Working Papers, No. 202, OECD Publishing, Paris.

- [3] Galan-Muros, V. and Plewa, C. (2016) *What drives and inhibits university-business cooperation in Europe? A comprehensive assessment*. R & D Management. Transferring Knowledge Special Issue. Vol.46, I.2, pp 303-399

- [4] “Architecture and Systems Engineering: Models and Methods to Manage Complex Systems”. As retrieved from <https://sysengonline.mit.edu> on May 3rd, 2018

- [5] The Institute-wide Task Force on the Future of MIT Education Final Report (2014), as retrieved on April 20, 2018 from <https://future.mit.edu/>.